

DYES DERIVED FROM ACENAPHTHENEQUINONE. PART X. 2-(7-CHLORO)-
THIONAPHTHENE-ACENAPHTHYLENE INDIGOS

BY SISIR KUMAR GUHA AND JNANENDRA NATH CHATTERJEE

7-Chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene has been condensed with acenaphthenequinone and some of its important derivatives and also aceanthrenequinone. The thioindigoid dyes of the 7-chloro series, described here, are lighter than those of the 5-chloro compounds studied previously.

This communication is an extension of the work of Guha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 679; 1936, 13, 94; 1938, 15, 20; 1943, 20, 37; 1944, 21, 91) which was studied with the object of examining the effect of a methyl radical when present in every available position of the thionaphthene ring of 2-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene indigos (Ciba scarlet G, Ciba red R etc.).

It deals with the preparation and a study of the properties of 2-(7-chloro)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene indigos which represent a new series of thioindigoid vat dyes of asymmetrical character and possess the general structural formula (I).

(I)

Acenaphthenequinone, its 3-chloro, 3-bromo and 1-methoxy derivatives have been condensed with 7-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (Dalglish and Mann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 893) respectively and the corresponding thioindigoid vat dyes obtained. These are yellowish red, red and deep red crystalline compounds, soluble in pyridine, xylene and nitrobenzene. The parent dye and its 3'-chloro and 3'-bromo derivatives are soluble in benzene, while the 1'-methoxy derivative is moderately soluble in the same solvent. They are all sparingly soluble in alcohol and CCl_4 except the 3'-chloro compound, which is moderately soluble in the latter.

In this class of dyes, the vat is produced between 50° and 60° by the action of alkaline hydrosulphite; it is noticed that during reduction, excess of caustic alkali turns the vat into a tarry product and hence it is carefully avoided. The dyeing shades were uniformly and fully developed on cotton from the hydrosulphite vat except in the case of the methoxy compound. Even after prolonged treatment the vat obtained from the 1'-methoxy dye was faint violet from which a uniform pink colour developed on atmospheric oxidation (*cf.* Goldstein and Schlenker, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1921, 4, 234; Guha, *loc. cit.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 127).

The dyeing shades, obtained from the compounds of this series, on wool from a dilute sulphuric acid bath are also quite uniform. Although lighter, these are more pleasant than those obtained from the 3-indole-2'-(7'-chloro)-thionaphthene indigos (Guha and Chatterjee, this *Journal*, 1947, 23, 473). A study of the colour of the compounds described here and their dyeing shades indicate (Table I) that they are lighter than those of the corresponding substances belonging to the 2-(5-chloro)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene indigo series (Guha, *loc. cit.*). A quantitative measurement of the change in colour due to the effect of a chlorine atom in the 5'-position and in the 7'-position of the thionaphthene ring of 2-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene indigos will be communicated afterwards.

TABLE I

A = acenaphthylene indigo	T = Thionaphthene.
Compounds.	Dyeing shade on cotton.
{ 2-(5-Chloro) T-A { 2-(7-Chloro) T-A	Dark red Red
{ 2-(5-Chloro) T-8'-(3'-chloro)-A { 2-(7-Chloro) T-8'-(3'-chloro)-A	Dark red Red
{ 2-(5-Chloro) T-8'-(3'-bromo)-A { 2-(7-Chloro) T-8'-(3'-bromo)-A	Dark red Deep red
{ 2-(5-Chloro) T-8'-(1'-methoxy)-A { 2-(7-Chloro) T-8'-(1'-methoxy)-A	Pink Pink (lighter shade)

Another asymmetrical thioindigoid dye, 2-(7-chloro)-thionaphthene-1'-accanthrylene indigo (II), has also been obtained now by condensing acenanthrenequinone (Liebermann and Zsuffa, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 209) with 7-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene. It is a brown colouring substance and lighter than that of the 2-(7-chloro)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene indigo (*loc. cit.*) which is yellowish red.

(II)

EXPERIMENTAL

2-(7-Chloro)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene indigo.—Acenaphthene quinone (0.546 g.) and 7-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.5535 g.) were dissolved in boiling glacial acetic acid (55 c. c.) and treated with strong hydrochloric acid (3.5 c. c.); the mixture was shaken when the crystalline yellowish red dye separated as a thick mass. Glacial acetic acid (70 c. c.) was further added and boiled for 25 a minutes, filtered hot, washed with

a little acetic acid and hot water, yield 0.745 g. It was crystallised from nitrobenzene in long, silky, pointed needles, m. p. 313-14°. It is soluble in acetic acid; strong sulphuric acid dissolves it producing a green solution. It dyes wool in yellowish red shade from an acid bath, and cotton in pleasant and attractive red shade from the violet vat formed by the action of alkaline hydrosulphite. (Found: C, 68.6; H, 2.6. $C_{20}H_8O_2ClS$ requires C, 68.89; H, 2.58 per cent).

2-(7-Chloro)-thionaphthene-8'-(3'-chloro)-acenaphthylene indigo was similarly prepared from 3-chloroacenaphthenequinone (0.6495 g.) and 7-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.5535 g.) in hot glacial acetic acid (70 c. c.) and strong hydrochloric acid (4 c. c.). The mixture containing the lumpy mass of the separated dye was again treated with glacial acetic acid (20 c. c.) and boiled for 25 minutes. The wooly, long, needle shaped red dye (0.879 g.) was crystallised from xylene in thin needles, m. p. 292-93°. It is moderately soluble in acetone. The solution of the substance in strong sulphuric acid is light green. The dyeing shade on wool is similar to, but slightly deeper than that obtained from the preceding compound. It dyes cotton in red shade from the blue alkaline hydrosulphite vat. (Found: C, 62.1; H, 2.3. $C_{20}H_8O_2Cl_2S$ requires C, 62.66; H, 2.08 per cent).

2-(7-Chloro)-thionaphthene-8'-(3'-bromo)-acenaphthylene indigo separated in deep red crystalline mass (0.678 g.) when a solution of 3-bromoacenaphthenequinone (0.652 g.) and 7-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.4612 g.) in glacial acetic acid (100 c. c.) was treated with strong hydrochloric acid (5 c. c.) and boiled for 20 minutes. It was crystallised from xylene in wooly clusters of needles, m. p. 281-83°. It is moderately soluble in acetic acid; it dissolves in strong sulphuric acid producing a light blue solution. It dyes wool from an acid bath in yellowish red shade which is deeper than those obtained from the 3'-chloro and the mother compound. Cotton is dyed in pleasant deep red shade from the violet-blue alkaline hydrosulphite vat. (Found: C, 55.4, 55.6; H, 1.8, 1.9. $C_{20}H_8O_2Cl BrS$ requires C, 56.14, H, 1.87 per cent).

2-(7-Chloro)-thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)-acenaphthylene indigo.—The light red solution, produced by dissolving β -methoxyacenaphthenequinone (0.742 g.) and 7-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.6457 g.) in glacial acetic acid (125 c. c.); on treatment with strong hydrochloric acid (5 c. c.) and boiling for 25 minutes separated a darkish red, fibrous crystalline dye (0.5812 g.). It was crystallised from nitrobenzene in wooly needles not melting below 320°. It is moderately soluble in benzene and acetic acid. The colour of the solution of the dye in strong sulphuric acid resembles that of the preceding compound. It dyes wool in darkish red from an acid bath and cotton in pink colour from the faint violet hydrosulphite vat. (Found: C, 66.1; H, 3.3. $C_{21}H_{11}O_3ClS$ requires C, 66.58; H, 2.9 per cent).

2-(7-Chloro)-thionaphthene-1'-aceanthrylene indigo.—Aceanthrenequinone (0.696 g.) and 7-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.5535 g.) were dissolved in boiling glacial acetic acid (125 c. c.) and treated with strong hydrochloric acid (6 c. c.). It was boiled for 30 minutes during which the brown crystalline dye separated gradually. The dye (0.682 g.) was washed successively with glacial acetic acid and dilute sodium hydroxide and finally with hot water. It was crystallised from nitrobenzene in small clusters of fibrous

needles not melting below 320° . It is soluble in pyridine, xylene, nitrobenzene and benzene; moderately soluble in glacial acetic acid; sparingly soluble in carbon tetrachloride; insoluble in alcohol. The solution of the substance in strong sulphuric acid is light green. It dyes wool in brown shade from an acid bath and cotton in red ochre shade from the light yellow hydrosulphite vat. (Found: C, 72.1; H, 2.3. $C_{22}H_{11}O_2ClS$ requires C, 72.28; H, 2.75 per cent).

CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
SCIENCE COLLEGE,
PATNA.

Received May 3, 1948.